

Search Strategy by Database

PubMed

Search terms:

- *multiple sclerosis* [MeSH] AND *rehabilitation* [MeSH] AND (*mixed reality* OR *augmented reality*)

Filters applied:

- Study design: Clinical trial, controlled clinical trial, clinical study

Web of Science

Search terms:

- Topic: *multiple sclerosis* AND *rehabilitation* AND (*mixed reality* OR *augmented reality*)

Filters applied:

- Study design: Clinical trial

PEDro

Search terms:

- *multiple sclerosis* AND *rehabilitation* AND *reality*

Cochrane Library

Search terms:

- *multiple sclerosis* AND *rehabilitation* AND (*mixed reality* OR *augmented reality*)

Scopus

Search terms:

- *multiple sclerosis* AND *rehabilitation* AND (*mixed reality* OR *augmented reality*)

Search fields: Title, abstract, and keywords

CINAHL

Search terms:

- (*multiple sclerosis*) AND ((*mixed reality* OR *augmented reality*))

Google Scholar

Search configuration:

- With all of the words: *multiple sclerosis*
- With the exact phrase: *mixed reality, augmented reality*

- Where the words occur: anywhere in the article